

THE BASIC NOTIONS OF COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY AND COMPARISON OF PECULIAR TYPE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the main notions of comparative typology in English and Uzbek and discusses the peculiarities of comparative typology as a science. Besides there are discussed certain correlations between the comparative typology and the other branches of general linguistics based on the method of comparison.

Keywords: comparative typology, notions of a type of a language and types of cases, suffix, linguistics, bilingualism.

Comparative Typology deals with comparing of language units and languages that do not share common root language play an important role in the emerging and developing of the subject. Comparison of structural languages that are not substantial also is crucial in the development of Comparative Typology. It is also the typology of Bilingualism and multilingualism, various issues of language contacts, which, in turn include problems of bilingualism, interference, convergence and many others. All these concepts are interconnected, and each of which is directly related to comparative typology. Linguistic issues occupy a large place in comparative typology. The problem of bilingualism is understood as the process of describing systems of mutually contacting languages, identifying systemic differences, determining differentiating means, etc. The use of comparative typology as an applied discipline can be carried out through the methodology of teaching foreign languages. When comparing systems of languages, typology determines the system features of each language. These distinguished abstracted models, representing certain cuts and speech activity, can serve as an additional material for the introduction of students into the world of another unknown language. This issue is of particular importance in teaching unrelated languages or languages with different structure. Researchers of any foreign language in their pedagogical activities inevitably encounter errors, and often numerous, which their students make both in pronunciation and in the structure of a foreign language, especially in oral and written language. Often, instead of one word, another is used,

and the compatibility of words accepted in a given language is violated, being affected by the compatibility standards of the Comparative typology operates with a limited number of languages and the minimum number of these languages maybe as little as two. Comparative typology cannot reveal language universals but it does contribute to Structural typology with the results of its comparative studies of concrete languages for further elaboration of linguistic universals. In its turn, Structural typology contributes to comparative typological studies while identifying correspondences in diverse languages.

The main purposes of comparative typology are:

- To identify and classify accordingly the main isomorphic and allomorphic features characteristic of languages under investigation;
- To draw from these common or divergent features respectively the isomorphic regularities and the allomorphic singularities in the languages contrasted;
- To establish on the basis of the obtained isomorphic features the typical language structures and the types of languages;
- To perform on the basis of the obtained practical data a truly scientific classification of the existing languages of the world;
- To establish on this basis the universal features/phenomena, which pertain to each single language of the world.

Comparative typology is closely linked with the following philological sciences:

1. General linguistics
2. Special linguistics
3. Comparative linguistics
4. Contrastive linguistics
5. Confrontative linguistics
6. Characterological linguistics
7. Typological linguistics
8. Historical comparative linguistics
9. Theory and practice of translation
10. Grammar
11. Phonetics
12. Stylistics
13. Textology
14. Lexicology
15. Lexicography
16. Phraseology
17. Phraseography

18. Pragmatic linguistics
19. Cognitive linguistics
20. Linguoculturology
21. Sociolinguistics
22. Psycholinguistics
23. Methods of teaching languages.

Comparative typology cooperates with all of these branches of linguistics in accordance with purposes and tasks of this or that investigation needed in both theoretical and applied linguistics, including interfacial sciences. Here are some attention to the main means of expressing the notions, which are of peculiar type for the comparing English and Uzbek languages.

The most commonly attested word orders are (Subject-object-verb)SOV and (Subject-verb-object) SVO while the least common orders are those that are object initial with (Object-verb-subject) OVS being the least common with only four attested instances. Typological category of case. The system of grammatical forms indicating the syntactic relations of nouns (or pronouns) is usually treated as the category of case, in other words, case is a grammatical form, which takes part in the formation of the paradigm of nouns or pronouns. Philologists seem to be divided in their opinion as to the case system of English nouns. The most common view is that they have only two cases: 1. Common case (subject); 2. Possessive case (genitive). The common case is characterized by a zero morpheme (suffix), for example: child, boy, student, girl and the possessive case by the inflexion -'s and its phonetic variants as [s] and [iz]. But Uzbek language has six cases such as: 1. Bosh kelishik; 2. Qaratqich kelishik; 3. Tushum kelishik; 4. O'rin-payt kelishik; 5. Jo'nalish kelishik; 6. Chiqish kelishik.

Bosh kelishik (common case) corresponds in meaning and function to the English common case; both of them are unmarked member of the case opposition and perform similar syntactic function (of a subject) in the sentence structure. English common case and other five cases of Uzbek are marked members of the case opposition in both languages. English possessive case is marked by the suffix -'s, which can sometimes be substituted by the preposition "of" (for example: his sister's bag – the bag of his sister) and sometimes is called "of genitive case. This case denotes possession of a thing or a person and in Uzbek it has its correspondence in Uzbek qaratqich kelishik, which is expressed by the case ending suffix – ning. Dealing with notion of possession one should keep in mind that in Uzbek this category may be expressed not only by the nouns but also their modifiers in the pleonastic phrases, such as Mening uyi-m, Sizning daftar-ingiz. In this case we have to face the problem of redundancy and often try to avoid it using the modified noun only, which contains the possessive suffix. For

example: Ona-m keldi. In this case the suffix of possession can be rendered in English and Russian by means of special possessive pronouns. For instance: My sister came. Моя мама пришла. Meanings and functions of the other Uzbek cases may be denoted in Uzbek either by means of prepositions by word order. For example: the meaning and function of Uzbek (tushum kelishik) is expressed in Uzbek by means of the case ending –ни, which denotes the object acted upon and it may be expressed in English by means of word order, which is characterized in this language to be very strict in comparison with Russian or Uzbek. Several English philologists, like O. Curme, M. and Deutschbein recognized word order in English as Dative case. Dealing with this case, one has to keep in mind the structure of the sentence, i.e. the word order in the sentences of the comparing languages – SOV (in Uzbek, e.g.: U kecha o'qituvchisini ko'rdi. and SVO (in English, e.g.: He saw his teacher. In Uzbek o'rin-payt kelishik denotes the place of the thing or a person in the space and it can be rendered in English by means of prepositions, like at, in, on, by, over, above, among, between, behind and etc. (e.g.: Китоб жавонда – The book is in the bookcase). It should be kept in mind that most of the English prepositions may contain (more) additional meaning denoting the place of the thing or a person (e.g.: in – ichi-da, behind – orqasida-da, between – orasi-da, under – osti-da, and etc.) The Uzbek jo'nalish kelishik denotes the direction of an action performed by the subject of the sentence and is expressed by means of the case ending –ga. It can be rendered in English also by means of prepositions, like to, at, into, and etc. For example: U (o'g'il bola) maktab-ga ketdi. He went to school. U (qiz bola) men-ga qaradi. She looked at me. Chiqish kelishik of Uzbek nouns denotes the beginning point of the action denoted by the verb. It can be rendered in English by means of prepositions, like from, out of, from under, etc. For instance: Ular Londondan keldi. – They came from London. Man sumkam-dan qo'lqoplarimni oldim.- I took my gloves out of my bag. The classification of human languages into different types on the basis of shared properties which are not due to common origin or geographical contact. Its aim is to describe and explain the common properties and the structural diversity of the world's languages. Simply speaking, the study of universals is concerned with what human languages have in common, while the study of typology deals with ways in which languages differ from each other.

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